

D2.1 Technical Specifications

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Introduction

This technical specifications document describes the user stories, workflows, user interfaces, and underlying technical implementations planned for the HORIZON-ZEN Plus project. The specifications are derived directly from the measurable results defined under Specific Objectives SO1, SO2, and SO3 of the project proposal.

The document serves as a reference for multiple work packages. Work Package 1 uses these specifications for planning, coordination, and monitoring purposes, while Work Package 3 relies on them to guide design and implementation activities. The specifications will be reviewed and updated periodically as part of Task 2.2 at the start of each release cycle.

Motivation

Horizon-Zen Plus aims to significantly reduce the human effort required to operate and support the EU Open Research Repository within Zenodo, enabling cost-effective scalability in the face of a continuously growing volume of research outputs. Data curation remains one of the most resource-intensive aspects of repository operations and represents a key bottleneck for sustainable growth.

A significant share of the operational effort required to run the EU Open Research Repository in Zenodo is spent handling repetitive and well-defined support requests. These include actions such as record deletion, quota increases, file modifications, and reports. The first objective of the project is therefore **to automate the handling of these standard support requests**. This improves response times for users and reduces the operational load on the Zenodo support and curation teams.

Data curation itself remains one of the most resource-intensive components of repository operations. The volume and heterogeneity of incoming submissions make fully manual curation unsustainable at scale, particularly when higher metadata quality is required to support FAIR and AI-ready reuse. To address this, the project **introduces AI-assisted curation tools that support curators** by automatically reviewing incoming submissions. These tools are designed to assist, not replace, human curators, allowing them to focus on content quality and edge cases rather than routine validation.

The project improves the deposit and discovery workflows to better support FAIR and AI-ready datasets. This includes support for AI-ready data packaging formats, enhanced metadata guidance during deposit, and improved subject classification to increase metadata completeness and consistency. Discovery capabilities are strengthened through advanced browsing, filtering, and the integration of citation and usage metrics to support more effective ranking and recommendation.

Together with AI-assisted curation and validation checks, these interventions improve the overall quality and reusability of published datasets while lowering the technical barrier for researchers to publish and reuse data in AI workflows.

Use of AI

The project foresees the development and deployment of artificial intelligence (AI). All AI components are designed in accordance with the principles of trustworthy AI, including transparency, fairness, accountability, and human oversight. The AI systems will not process personal data, nor will they make legally or ethically consequential decisions. The project develops and deploys AI in two main use cases:

- **Funding validation:** A pre-trained large language model is used in combination with deterministic heuristics to verify whether submitted records contain valid funding information. Records that cannot be confidently verified are delegated to Zenodo support staff for human curation.
- **Subject classification:** A dedicated AI model will be fine-tuned to classify records into the EuroSciVoc controlled vocabulary. The training data is sourced from CORDIS, covering all previously funded EU projects.

All AI systems in the project are developed and deployed in line with the EU's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and the Ethics by Design and Ethics of Use framework. The following ethical safeguards are implemented:

- **Transparency and explainability:** The use of AI will be clearly labelled in all relevant workflows. Users (curators and submitters) will be informed when AI is involved, and explanations of decisions, such as classification suggestions or funding validation outcomes, will be made accessible.
- **Accountability and oversight:** All AI models, performance metrics, training data, and source code will be openly shared. This enables independent auditing and fosters community trust. Audit logs of all AI-assisted decisions will be maintained and made accessible to both submitters and curators. All AI accepted submissions will be monitored monthly by Zenodo staff to detect problems.
- **Fairness and bias mitigation:** The only model trained in the project is the subject classification model, which will be trained on the full corpus of CORDIS representative of the diversity of all EU-funded research.
- **User rights and appeal:** Users can flag and report issues or object to AI-assisted decisions (e.g. classification errors) through existing reporting mechanisms. Submissions that cannot be automatically verified or are contested will be reviewed by human curators following Zenodo's curation policies and procedures.
- **Auditability:** All AI-assisted decisions will be logged and traceable. Submitters and curators will be able to review the history of decisions, including model outputs and confidence scores, ensuring full accountability.

Data privacy & security aspects

The project does not foresee processing of personal data as part of the new technical developments. Zenodo operates under a documented privacy policy compliant with CERN Operational Circular No. 11.

Use of AI is scoped as decision support. AI-assisted components are designed according to trustworthy AI principles, including transparency, accountability, and human oversight. AI outputs are labelled, explainable, and subject to review or override by users or curators. AI systems do not process personal data and do not make legally or ethically consequential decisions.

Security controls apply across model serving and the repository workflows. Models are hosted locally on CERN infrastructure and the system maintains traceability of AI assisted decisions through logging, including outputs and confidence indicators, to support auditability and incident analysis.

User rights and contestability are preserved. Users can flag issues or object to AI assisted outcomes (for example misclassification), and submissions that cannot be automatically verified are reviewed by human curators following Zenodo curation policies.

Data export and repatriation follow Zenodo privacy constraints. Public metadata and public files can be exported directly. For personal data and closed files, user consent is requested before export, in line with the privacy policy commitments described in the proposal.

SO1: Support automation

SO1 aims to reduce the manual effort and operational cost of running the EU Open Research Repository in Zenodo by automating standard support requests and introducing AI-assisted curation workflows. The objective is to handle repetitive, policy-driven tasks automatically while supporting human curators with targeted validation tools for more complex cases.

All solutions under SO1 are designed with human oversight, transparency, and auditability, ensuring that automated decisions remain explainable, reversible, and safely routed to manual review when needed.

Automated record deletion

Submitters can request the deletion of a record through a dedicated workflow in the system. Deletion requests that are eligible under the policy are processed automatically without manual support intervention.

After publication, the user can edit an existing record and trigger the deletion workflow using the new “Delete record” action available on the deposit form page (figure 1). If the request falls outside the allowed policy window, the action is disabled and a clear explanation is shown to the user.

Figure 1: New “Delete record” in the deposit form when editing an existing record

The action opens the following confirmation modal (figure 2):

Delete record

Deleting this record will delete **two** files.

<Instance> DOIs cannot be reused and the DOI will resolve to a [tombstone page](#)

I want to delete this record because*:

- I made a mistake in the metadata (title, description, authors, etc)
- There is a problem with the files
- This is a duplicate of another record
- I was testing uploading to Zenodo
- Other

Comment*:

Zenodo has a [30 day grace period](#). 28 days remain to delete this record immediately.

Figure 2: Delete record modal

After providing the required information and confirming the action, the record is deleted immediately. The record landing page is replaced by a tombstone page indicating that the record has been removed and displaying the selected deletion reason.

Automated file modification

Submitters can replace or remove files of a published record within the allowed policy window through an automated workflow, without requiring manual support intervention.

When editing a published record, the “Edit published files” action is available as long as the record remains within the file modification grace period (figure 3).

Figure 3: New “Edit files” box in the deposit form when editing an existing record

Selecting this action opens a guided confirmation dialogue that explains the policy constraints and requires the submitter to explicitly confirm that the modification does not affect the scientific findings or results of the published work (figure 4).

Figure 4: New “Edit files” modal when replacing files

If the submitter indicates that a substantive change is required, the workflow redirects them to create a new version instead (figure 5).

Figure 5: New “Edit files” modal when selecting a new version

Once confirmed, file editing is enabled immediately and the submitter can replace or remove files. The modified files must be published within a limited time window, after which the record is locked again. All automated checks and constraints are enforced by policy, and requests falling outside the allowed scope are prevented at the interface level with clear user feedback.

Improved curation interface

To reduce operational effort and improve throughput, the curation, and administration interface supports faster triage and handling of incoming requests and curation actions. The primary goal is to help curators and supporters immediately identify what requires attention, distinguish new items from ongoing conversations, and prioritise work based on the most recent activity rather than creation time alone.

The interface provides clear request and record states to separate:

- items that have not yet received an initial response,
- items awaiting input from the submitter,
- items pending curator action after a submitter has replied,
- items resolved or closed.

In the administration panel, the status field supports filtering by these states to enable focused work queues. Sorting options include ordering by newest and oldest activity, allowing curators to prioritise items with recent user interactions and avoid missing follow-ups in long-running threads (figure 6).

Figure 6: Improved information and sorting in administration panel

Automated new projects information

When creating a new EU project community, the system automatically populates community metadata from the selected EU grant by retrieving authoritative project information from CORDIS. The pre-filled fields include the community name, short description, project website, and participating organisations (figure 7).

This reduces manual data entry and prevents common copy and paste errors, improving both correctness and completeness of project communities. It also reduces the support burden by limiting back-and-forth exchanges to correct incomplete or inconsistent community metadata.

Setup your new EU project community

Create a community for your Horizon Europe or other EU-funded project to collect and share research outputs.

i Institutional email required. To verify your affiliation with the project, you must use an email address from one of the project's partner institutions, or have connected your account via your institution's login. [Learn more](#)

Is there already an existing community for your project?

Yes No

Project *

FAIRCORE4EOSC

Grant 101057344 · FAIR components for the European Open Science Cloud

Community details **✎ Auto-filled**

Community name

FAIRCORE4EOSC - FAIR components for the European Open Science Cloud

You can edit this to customize your community name.

Identifier

zenodo.org/communities/ faircore4eosc

Short description

FAIR components for the European Open Science Cloud

Website

https://faircore4eosc.eu

Organizations **✎ Auto-filled** ⓘ

CE CERN Switzerland

Coordinator

CS CSIC Spain

TU TU Delft Netherlands

You can add or remove organizations after the community is created.

Create community

Figure 7: EU project creation form with metadata autofilled from CORDIS

For existing project communities, an additional action in the community settings allows administrators to refresh previously entered metadata from CORDIS to correct or complete outdated or incomplete fields.

Future extensions

This section describes candidate enhancements that are aligned with the project objectives but are not committed for delivery at this stage. Their implementation will depend on observed support effort, user demand, and available capacity during the release cycles. If prioritised, these extensions will be specified through the same RFC process and integrated into the roadmap based on impact on operations and user experience.

Automated quota increase

Submitters can request an increase in the storage quota to upload larger files through an automated, policy-driven workflow. Requests that fall within the defined quota limits are approved immediately without manual intervention.

During the upload process, when a user reaches the storage quota limit and is eligible for an increase, an “Increase storage” action becomes available in the upload form (figure 8).

Figure 8: New action “Increase storage” in the files upload form

Selecting this action opens a dedicated panel that displays the current storage usage, the default quota, and the maximum additional storage available under the policy. The user can adjust the requested increase up to the allowed limit and confirm the request (figure 9). Quota increases beyond the automated limit are not available through this workflow and must be requested via a support ticket.

Figure 9: New storage increase panel

In the new “My account → Storage” view, users can review their storage usage at any time, including the default quota, additional storage granted, remaining available quota, and a per-record breakdown of how the additional storage is allocated (figure 10).

Figure 10: New storage dashboard in My Account → Storage

Advanced validation checks for projects

After a user submits a request to create a new EU project community, the system runs a set of validation checks to ensure the community is legitimate, correctly linked to an active EU grant, and compliant with EOR onboarding requirements. The checks are displayed in the request workflow under the Checks tab and are grouped by topic to support quick triage and clear remediation steps (figure 11).

Figure 11: Checks summary for an EU project request.

The system verifies that at least one community member with a privileged role (owner or manager) is affiliated with one of the project’s participating organisations. Affiliation is verified either by matching the member’s institutional email domain against the project partner list, or by confirming the member through a connected institutional login. The check provides the evidence used for verification for each relevant member (figure 12).

Member affiliation

Verifies that at least one community member (owner or manager) is affiliated with one of the EU project's participating organizations.

Community owner is affiliated with a project organization

Maria García
m.garcia@csic.es · Owner

The community owner's email domain (csic.es) matches CSIC, which is listed as a partner organization for this project.
[Learn more](#)

Verified via connected institutional account

Maria García
m.garcia@csic.es · Owner

The community owner has connected their account via OpenAIRE AAI, confirming their affiliation with CSIC.
[Learn more](#)

Community manager is affiliated with a project organization

Lars Holm Nielsen
lars.holm.nielsen@cern.ch · Manager

The community manager's email domain (cern.ch) matches CERN, which is listed as the project coordinator.
[Learn more](#)

What is this about?

To ensure communities are managed by legitimate project participants, we verify that at least one community member (owner or manager) is affiliated with one of the project's partner organizations.

How do we verify affiliation?

We check the member's email domain against the project's partner organizations, or verify through connected institutional accounts (e.g., via your institution's login).
[Learn more](#)

Figure 12: Member affiliation check.

The system validates the selected EU grant and prevents duplicate onboarding of the same project. This includes confirming that the grant exists and is active, and checking whether an EU project community already exists for the same grant (figure 13).

Figure 13: Project validation.

When adding an existing project to the EU repository, the system evaluates records in the community and detects missing or inconsistent funding statements. Where gaps exist, the interface reports how many records are affected and provides an action to add the project funding metadata in bulk (figure 14).

Figure 14: Validation of existing records.

Community metadata is automatically suggested on submission. The curation interface (figure 15) ensures its correctness and completeness.

The screenshot displays a web interface for metadata validation. At the top, there are two tabs: 'Conversation' and 'Checks'. The 'Checks' tab is active. On the left side, there is a vertical list of check categories: 'Member affiliation', 'Project validation', 'Funding metadata', and 'Community metadata'. The 'Community metadata' category is selected and highlighted. The main content area is titled 'Suggested community metadata' and contains a sub-header: 'The following metadata was automatically suggested based on the selected EU project.' Below this, there are five metadata items, each with a green checkmark icon: 'Name' (FAIRCORE4EOSC - FAIR components for the European Open Science Cloud), 'Identifier' (faircore4eosc), 'Short description' (FAIRCORE4EOSC develops components for the European Open Science Cloud that enable findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable research.), 'Website' (https://faircore4eosc.eu), and 'Organizations'. The 'Organizations' section lists six entities: CERN (Switzerland) with a 'Coordinator' role, CSIC (Spain), TU Delft (Netherlands), Ghent University (Belgium), ATHENA RC (Greece), and CIEMAT (Spain). On the right side, there is a text box titled 'What is this about?' explaining that the metadata is suggested based on EU project information. Below it, a section titled 'Can I edit this metadata?' states that the community owner can edit all metadata after creation. A 'Learn more' link is provided at the bottom of this section.

Figure 15: Metadata validation.

SO1: AI-assisted submission and curation

AI-assisted curation checks for records

Existing automated checks based on static rules are complemented by advanced checks that are integrated directly into the deposit workflow to detect common metadata quality issues as early as possible. Where appropriate, these advanced checks use AI-assisted validation to improve detection beyond what static rules can reliably capture. The checks run during deposit editing and are re-evaluated during curation to ensure consistency at publication time.

The following checks are added:

- Funding metadata completeness and correctness. The AI-assisted validation compares the record metadata with the official grant description from the CORDIS database and flags potential mismatches for review.
- Detection of misclassified author entities, for example organisations entered as personal authors. This is detected using heuristics such as token count, character patterns, and keyword cues that indicate an organisation name rather than a personal name.
- Detection of incorrectly formatted full-text pastes in description fields, such as copy-pasted full papers or large unstructured blocks that reduce metadata quality. This is detected using formatting and content heuristics, for example unusually long text, excessive line breaks, and citation-like patterns.
- Identification of incomplete or inconsistent mandatory metadata fields, including missing required elements or invalid combinations of values.

In parallel, the [AIRDEC project](#) develops AI-assisted deposition directly in the submission form to detect and prevent this class of metadata issues more comprehensively at the point of entry. This complements or replaces the heuristic checks described above and provides a path to improved accuracy over time.

Figure 16 illustrates the AI-assisted funding validation in the curation interface. The check flags a potential mismatch between the record metadata and the selected grant description and clearly indicates that the result is AI-generated. The interface provides an explanation and a link to further information so that the submitter or curator can assess the warning. This check is advisory and does not block submission.

Figure 16: AI-assisted funding validation as advanced checks

Direct submissions to the EOR Repository

For direct submissions to the EOR Repository, the system triggers the same AI-assisted funding validation to verify that the record title and description are consistent with the selected EU grant. The validation compares the submitted metadata against the official grant description retrieved from CORDIS and flags potential mismatches for review.

Harvesting workflows

In addition to direct submissions to the EOR Repository, many EU-funded outputs are deposited on Zenodo outside EU project communities, and some EU-funded projects create Zenodo communities that are not included as EU project communities within the EOR Repository. Zenodo therefore runs harvesting workflows that identify both candidate records and candidate project communities across the broader Zenodo platform.

HORIZON-ZEN+ enhances this existing harvesting workflow by applying the same validation approach used for direct submissions. For records, the pipeline uses AI-assisted matching to compare the record title and description against EU grant descriptions from CORDIS to infer likely project association, even when funding metadata is missing or incomplete. For communities, the pipeline evaluates community metadata (name, description, and related identifiers) against EU grant information to detect communities that likely correspond to EU-funded projects but have not been onboarded into the EU project community framework.

This extends funding validation and metadata quality assessments beyond the deposit interface and enables discovery of additional EU-funded records and projects that would otherwise remain outside the EOR Repository due to incomplete or missing funding metadata.

SO2: AI-ready dataset and metadata

SO2 targets two practical barriers for AI reuse: discovering suitable datasets and loading them into AI workflows with minimal effort. The project addresses this by adding support for one AI-dataset packaging format and by introducing AI-specific dataset metadata that improves both reuse and discovery.

AI-ready refers to datasets that can be discovered and reused in AI workflows with minimal integration effort. In this document, the term ML-ready is used as a concrete indicator that a dataset provides machine-readable structure metadata in a supported format (e.g. Croissant). A dataset marked ML-ready is therefore considered AI-ready from a packaging and loading perspective, while broader AI readiness aspects (for example provenance and quality signals) are captured through additional AI-specific metadata fields described below.

Zenodo supports at least one AI-ready data packaging format, Croissant, as the standard mechanism to describe dataset structure in a machine actionable way (for example splits, label schema, and file organisation). This enables “load with minimal code” reuse patterns in notebooks and ML pipelines.

At this stage, the specification defines the capability and extensibility rather than locking a final field list. The concrete field set and guidance will be aligned with external stakeholders and EU projects producing AI-ready datasets, and with widely adopted practices in the AI ecosystem.

Deposit workflow changes (upload step)

1. Automatic detection

During file upload, the system scans the deposit file list for a recognised Croissant descriptor (for example croissant.json). When detected, the UI highlights the file and shows an informational banner explaining that the dataset includes standard

documentation and that this improves reuse and discovery (figure 17).

Figure 17: Croissant file auto-detected during upload

2. Manual declaration

If no AI-ready file is detected, the UI provides an explicit option to declare it. The depositor selects the format (Croissant) and selects which uploaded file is the descriptor. This supports cases where naming conventions differ or where detection is not possible

(figure 18).

Figure 18: Manual declaration of AI-ready file

AI-specific dataset metadata

The AI-specific dataset metadata fields improves machine-actionability and discovery. These fields capture information that users typically need to evaluate datasets for AI workflows and that cannot be reliably derived from file lists alone.

The AI-specific metadata covers three categories that reflect how users typically select datasets for AI workflows: modality, format, and ML tasks.

Modality describes the type of data contained in the dataset (for example tabular, image, text, audio, video, geospatial). Format describes the primary file or packaging formats used to distribute the dataset (for example CSV, Parquet, JSON, Arrow, image archives, WebDataset, Croissant). Tasks describe the intended or supported machine learning use cases (for example image classification, object detection, text classification, speech recognition, time series forecasting), grouped by domain.

These fields are indexed and exposed as search facets to enable precise filtering and dedicated browsing of datasets.

Record landing page changes

On published records that include AI-ready files, the landing page (figure 19) displays:

- An “ML Ready” indicator for quick recognition.
- A dedicated section that provides a minimal code snippet to load the dataset using the Croissant entry point, plus a direct download action for the descriptor file.
- Links to the metadata schema or documentation for the supported format.

Dataset
Open Access
ML-Ready

European Climate Image Dataset for Deep Learning v2.0

Müller, Anna · García, Carlos · van den Berg, Erik · +4 authors

Published: August 15, 2024 | Version 2.0 | DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8234567](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8234567)

A comprehensive collection of 150,000 labeled satellite and ground-level images capturing European climate patterns from 2010-2024. Includes cloud formations, precipitation patterns, temperature anomalies, and seasonal variations across 28 European countries. Optimized for training deep learning models for climate prediction and weather pattern recognition.

Files 5
^

training_images.tar.gz	8.4 GB ↓
validation_images.tar.gz	2.1 GB ↓
labels.csv	45 MB ↓
metadata.json	128 KB ↓
croissant.json ML-ready metadata	24 KB ↓

Total size: 10.5 GB Download all files

ML-Ready (Croissant) NEW
^

Load this dataset directly into your ML pipeline using the Croissant metadata format:

Python
Copy code

```
import mlcroissant as mlc

ds = mlc.Dataset("https://zenodo.org/records/8234567/files/croissant.json")

# Iterate over the dataset records
for record in ds.records("images"):
    image = record["image"]
    label = record["category"]
    # Your training code here...
```

Installation: `pip install mlcroissant`

[Download croissant.json](#)
[View metadata schema](#) →
Compatible with: PyTorch TensorFlow JAX

Dataset Structure

Record sets:

- images (150,000 records)
- labels (150,000 records)

Fields:

- image (PNG, 256×256)
- category (string)
- timestamp (datetime)
- location (lat, lon)

Figure 19: ML-ready badge and Croissant loader snippet on record page

Enhanced discovery capabilities

This project extends discovery beyond the generic search UI by introducing a dedicated dataset browsing experience (figure 20) with advanced filtering and ranking tailored to AI-ready datasets. It supports the proposal objectives of advanced search and filtering, and usage based featuring to improve findability and recommendation-based discovery.

The screenshot displays a dataset portal interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the placeholder text "Search datasets..." and a "Search" button. Below the search bar, the interface shows "Showing 812,456 datasets" and a "Sort by: Trending" dropdown menu. On the left side, there is a "Filters" panel with a "Clear all (4)" link. The filters are organized into several categories:

- Modality:** Includes checkboxes for Tabular (checked, 67'234), Image (18'923), Text (34'567), Audio (4'532), Video (1'234), and Geospatial (8'976). A "Show 1 more..." link is also present.
- Format:** Includes checkboxes for CSV (checked, 45'892), Parquet (23'456), JSON (18'934), Arrow (8'934), Images (ZIP/TAR) (12'456), and WebDataset (3'421).
- Tasks:** Includes checkboxes for Image Classification (checked, 18'923), Object Detection (8'456), and Image Segmentation (4'532).
- COMPUTER VISION:** Includes checkboxes for Text Classification (34'567), Question Answering (12'456), and Translation (8'934).
- AUDIO:** Includes checkboxes for Automatic Speech Recognition (4'532), Audio Classification (2'345), and Text-to-Speech (1'890).
- TABULAR:** Includes checkboxes for Tabular Classification (12'345), Tabular Regression (8'765), and Time Series Forecasting (3'456).
- MULTIMODAL:** Includes checkboxes for Image-Text-to-Text (5'678), Visual Question Answering (3'421), and Video Classification (1'234).
- GEOSPATIAL:** Includes checkboxes for Remote Sensing (4'567), Climate Modeling (2'345), and GIS Analysis (1'890).
- Dataset documentation:** Includes checkboxes for Croissant (checked, 12'456) and HuggingFace (15'678).

The main content area displays a list of datasets, each with a title, a description, and various tags. The first dataset is "European Climate Observations 2020-2024" (ML-Ready), described as a comprehensive climate dataset covering temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric conditions across European monitoring stations. It is available in Tabular, CSV, Parquet, and Time Series formats, with 12.5M rows and 2.4 GB. The second dataset is "ImageNet-Mini: Subset for Quick Prototyping" (ML-Ready), a curated subset of ImageNet containing 50,000 images across 100 categories, optimized for rapid model development and testing. It is available in Image, WebDataset, and Images formats, with 50K rows and 1.2 GB. The third dataset is "Multilingual Speech Corpus v3" (ML-Ready), featuring speech recordings in 25 European languages with aligned transcriptions, suitable for ASR and speech synthesis research. It is available in Audio, Audio, JSON, Speech Recognition, and Text-to-Speech formats, with 1.2M rows and 8.7 GB. The fourth dataset is "CORD-19: COVID-19 Research Papers", a full-text corpus of COVID-19 and coronavirus research papers with structured metadata for NLP applications. It is available in Text, JSON, Parquet, Text Classification, and Question Answering formats, with 890K rows and 12.3 GB. The fifth dataset is "Sentinel-2 Land Cover Europe" (ML-Ready), featuring Sentinel-2 satellite imagery with pixel-wise land cover annotations for training semantic segmentation models. It is available in Geospatial, GeoTIFF, Parquet, Image Segmentation, and Remote Sensing formats, with 2.3M rows and 15.3 GB. The sixth dataset is "Financial News Sentiment Dataset" (ML-Ready), featuring annotated financial news articles with sentiment labels and entity mentions for NLP model training. It is available in Text, CSV, JSON, Text Classification, and Summarization formats, with 156K rows and 234 MB. At the bottom of the list, there is a pagination control showing "← Previous 1 2 3 ... 100 Next →".

Figure 20: Dataset portal with advanced filters and ML Ready tagging

The interface provides dataset focused filtering based on properties that users typically know upfront when searching for data. Candidate facets include dataset modality (for example tabular, image, text, audio, video, geospatial), file or packaging format (for example CSV, Parquet, JSON, WebDataset, Croissant), and common ML task categories (for example computer vision, NLP, speech, time series). These facets improve precision by allowing users to narrow large result sets using terms that correspond to how datasets are selected in practice.

Datasets that meet the project's definition of AI ready are visually tagged as "ML ready" in the search results list item. This provides a clear, low friction signal that the dataset includes machine actionable structure metadata in a supported format, improving discoverability of AI ready datasets without requiring users to open each record.

SO2: AI-assisted subject classification

This feature reduces the burden on depositors while improving metadata completeness and consistency for discovery. Subject metadata is a key input for browsing and filtering, yet it is often missing or inconsistent because users do not want to manually navigate long controlled vocabularies during deposit. The project therefore introduces automated subject classification as an initial step towards more automated metadata enrichment in deposit workflows.

During deposit editing (figure 21), the submitter can trigger an automatic subject suggestion action from the Subjects field. The system analyses the record metadata available at deposit time, primarily title, description, and other descriptive fields, and returns a ranked list of suggested subjects. Suggestions are expressed using the EuroSciVoc vocabulary to ensure standardisation and interoperability. The submitter remains in control: proposed subjects are not applied automatically and require explicit approval before they are added to the record.

Figure 21: Auto suggested subjects matching metadata with EuroSciVoc

The subject classification model is implemented as a dedicated AI service. It is fine-tuned for EuroSciVoc and trained using EU project context, including CORDIS derived information, to improve accuracy for EU funded research outputs. In addition to providing the suggested subjects, the service returns confidence indicators that help the UI present results in a usable way.

This capability is integrated into the deposit workflow and can be re-run when the changes are saved. It is also available to curators during review to help correct incomplete subject metadata before publication.

In parallel, the [AIRDEC project](#) develops broader AI-assisted deposition directly in the submission form, aiming to detect and prevent common metadata issues across multiple fields. Automated subject classification in HORIZON-ZEN Plus is designed to be compatible with that direction and can later be expanded into a more comprehensive AI-assisted metadata enrichment experience.

SO2: Geospatial metadata and vocabularies

The system supports the capture, validation, and reuse of geospatial metadata in both the deposit workflow and the open data discovery interface. This functionality enables submitters to describe the geographic scope of their research outputs in a structured and machine-actionable way, and allows users to discover and filter records based on geographic criteria.

To ensure interoperability and consistent naming, the deposit workflow integrates the [GeoNames](#) vocabulary for place lookup and resolution. GeoNames provides stable identifiers and standardised place names that reduce ambiguity (for example cities with the same name in different countries) and improve downstream reuse in indexing, aggregation, and geospatial search. Using a controlled vocabulary also improves the quality of facets and filters in discovery because locations can be normalised and mapped to higher-level regions.

The implementation builds on needs identified in HORIZON-ZEN, in particular through the iMagine project and the EyeOnWater training dataset use case, where geographic context is essential for data reuse and analysis.

Geospatial metadata in the deposit workflow

During deposit, submitters can optionally specify the geographic coverage of a record. Geographic coverage can be expressed using one or more named locations and, where relevant, a bounding box or polygon geometry.

The deposit form (figure 22) provides:

- A searchable location field backed by controlled geographic vocabularies
- Interactive map-based selection to define spatial extent
- Automatic generation of bounding box metadata from selected geometries
- Support for multiple geographic areas per record

Selected locations and geometries are stored as structured geospatial metadata and associated with the record at publication time.

Figure 22: Deposit form section for geographic coverage with map-based selection and location search

Geospatial metadata on record landing pages

For published records that include geographic metadata, the record landing page (figure 23) displays a dedicated geographic coverage section. This section presents the selected locations and spatial extent in both textual and visual form.

The display includes:

- A list of geographic locations associated with the record
- A rendered map showing the bounding box or polygon
- Normalized geographic metadata suitable for reuse by machines and aggregators

This presentation makes geographic scope immediately visible to users and improves interpretability of datasets with spatial relevance.

Figure 23: Record landing page showing geographic coverage summary and rendered map

Geospatial metadata in discovery and search

Geospatial metadata is indexed and exposed in the discovery interface (figure 24) to enable geographic filtering and browsing of records. Users can filter search results using geographic facets based on standardized geographic vocabularies and spatial hierarchies.

The discovery interface supports:

- Faceted filtering by geographic regions (e.g. continent, country)
- Free-text search over geographic locations
- Map-assisted selection to refine search results
- Combination of geographic filters with other facets (resource type, subject, access status)

Geographic facets reflect the underlying structured metadata and update dynamically based on the current result set.

5,834,973 result(s) found

Search results page interface showing filters and results.

Filters:

- Versions: View all versions
- Access status:
- Resource types:
- Geographic coverage** (highlighted with a dashed purple box):
 - Search location:
 - Europe (892'345)
 - North America (654'231)
 - Asia (521'098)
 - Africa (234'567)
 - South America (187'654)
 - Oceania (98'765)
 - Antarctica (12'456)
- Subjects:
- File type:

Results:

- February 1, 2026 (nightly)**
European Forest Biodiv
García, M., Nielsen, L.H., e
Comprehensive dataset cc
counts, habitat assessmer
📍 Spain, France, Portugal
Uploaded on February 1, 2
- January 31, 2026 (v1)**
Mediterranean Climate
Smith, J., et al.
Climate measurements fro
2015-2025.
📍 Italy, Greece, Spain
Uploaded on January 31, 2
- January 28, 2026 (v2)**
Alpine Ecosystem Surv
Müller, S., Weber, K.
Survey data from alpine ec
📍 Switzerland, Austria, Fr.
Uploaded on January 28, :

Figure 24: Search results page with geographic coverage facet and location-based filtering

SO2: New citation sources and usage metrics

The search and discovery interfaces integrate citation and usage metrics to improve ranking, filtering, and visibility of research outputs. Citation counts, views, and downloads are ingested from multiple trusted sources and made available both on record landing pages and in the search index.

Citation data sources and ingestion

Citation metadata is ingested from multiple external sources and consolidated per record and version. Existing citation sources are extended with additional providers, including [INSPIRE-HEP](#), to improve coverage for domain-specific literature. In addition, citations are harvested from the [European Geosciences Union](#) (EGU), through Copernicus Publications, using its OAI-PMH endpoint. This increases coverage for journals that frequently cite Zenodo records, such as [Earth System Science Data](#) and [Geoscientific Model Development](#).

Each citation entry is normalised and linked to the cited Zenodo record, preserving provenance information about the source of the citation. Citation data is refreshed periodically and exposed consistently across the user interface, search index, and APIs.

Citation metrics in record landing pages

For records with citation data, the landing page displays aggregated citation counts alongside views and downloads (figure 25). Users can inspect individual citations, filter them by type (e.g. literature, software, dataset), and identify the citation source.

Citation counts are version-aware and clearly indicate whether citations refer to a specific version or to all versions of a record.

The screenshot shows a 'Citations' page with 47 items. The interface includes a filter for 'Show only' (Literature, Software, Dataset) and a search bar. The list contains the following items:

Title	Year	Source(s)
Climate Change Impacts on European Forest Ecosystems: A Comprehensive Review Fernández, A., Schmidt, K., et al. (DOI: 10.1038/s41558-024-01234-5)	2025	OpenAlex, DOI
Biodiversity Monitoring in Protected Areas: Methods and Best Practices Van der Berg, J., Rossi, M. (DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.109876)	2025	Semantic Scholar, DOI
Mediterranean Forest Species Distribution Models v2.0 EcoData Consortium (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.9876543)	2025	DataCite, DOI
Machine Learning Approaches for Species Richness Prediction Liu, W., Andersson, P., et al. (DOI: 10.1111/ecog.2025.12345)	2025	DOI, OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar
BiodiversityMetrics: R package for ecological analysis v3.2 EcoStats Team (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8765432)	2024	DataCite, DOI
Carbon Sequestration in European Temperate Forests Under Climate Scenarios Dubois, C., Weber, H., Martinez, L. (DOI: 10.5194/bg-2024-567)	2024	EGU, DOI
Pan-European Tree Cover Change Dataset 2000-2024 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7654321)	2024	OpenAlex, DataCite
High-Energy Particle Effects on Forest Canopy Measurements Petrov, N., Kim, S., et al. (DOI: 10.1007/JHEP2024-0456)	2024	INSPIREHEP, DOI

Figure 25: Record landing page showing citations list with multiple sources, including INSPIRE Hep

Citation metrics in search ranking and sorting

Citation metrics are indexed in the search engine and can be used as explicit sorting criteria. When sorting by citations, views, or downloads, results are ranked using the corresponding aggregated values (figure 26) to provide consistent and transparent ordering.

5,834,973 result(s) found Sort by **Most cited** ▾

Versions View all versions

Access status ▾

Resource types

- Publication 3,711,710
- Image 1,163,502
- Dataset 537,210
- Software 210,850

Subjects ▾

File type ▾

February 1, 2026 (v3) Dataset Open

Global Climate Dataset v3.2

Smith, J., García, M., Nielsen, L.H.

Comprehensive global climate measurements from 1900 to 2024, including temperature, precipitation, and wind levels collected from weather stations worldwide.

Uploaded on February 1, 2026 👁 45'123 📄 12'456 📄 234 citations

January 15, 2026 (v2) Dataset Open

European Temperature Anomalies 1950-2023

Climate Research Institute

Historical temperature anomaly data for European regions, showing deviations from baseline measurements and long-term climate trends.

Uploaded on January 15, 2026 👁 32'456 📄 8'765 📄 187 citations

Figure 26: Search results page with sorting dropdown highlighting “Most cited”

In addition to sorting, these metrics are used to support featuring of high quality and trending datasets, for example through dedicated browsing collections and highlighted results. The exact featuring approach is refined based on user research and feedback. This includes discussions with users to understand what “good” and “trending” means in practice for different communities, and to select the most effective and appropriate promotion mechanisms.

SO3: EOSC EU Node integration

Zenodo supports authentication through the EOSC EU Node Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) (figure 27). When users log in via EOSC AAI, Zenodo uses the attributes released by the identity provider to automatically verify accounts where possible.

In particular, affiliation information (for example the research organisation domain or faculty context) is used to determine whether the user belongs to a recognised research institution. If the available attributes are sufficient, verification is applied automatically.

This feature relies on the EOSC EU Node AAI providing the necessary attributes consistently in production.

The image shows a screenshot of the Zenodo login interface. At the top, the Zenodo logo is displayed in white on a blue background. Below the logo, the text "Log in to account" is centered. There are four buttons for social login: "Sign in with ORCID", "Sign in with GitHub", "Sign in with OpenAIRE", and "Sign in with EOSC AAI". The "Sign in with EOSC AAI" button is highlighted with a dashed pink border. Below these buttons, there is an "OR" separator. Underneath, there are two input fields: "Email Address" and "Password". A blue "Log in" button is positioned below the input fields. At the bottom of the form, there are links for "New to Zenodo? Sign up", "Privacy notice", "Forgot password?", and "Resend confirmation email".

Figure 27: EOSC AAI login option

SO3: Integration with ORE

The EOR Repository provides a dedicated browsing experience for Open Research Europe publications by harvesting all eligible articles into the existing ORE community on Zenodo and exposing them through a dedicated ORE entry point in discovery.

After the migration of Open Research Europe to its new platform, ORE deposits publications directly into the ORE community on Zenodo, including the required metadata for EOR processing. The harvesting workflow ingests new and updated ORE records from the community feed and performs the same validation and enrichment steps used elsewhere in the EOR pipeline.